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**Comparison of rumen and abomasal infusions of an exogenous emulsifier on
fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows**

J. M. dos Santos Neto, C. M. Prom,* and A. L. Lock†

Department of Animal Science, Michigan State University, East Lansing 48824

*Current address: Cargill Inc., 15407 McGinty Rd W, Wayzata, MN 55391.

†Corresponding author: Adam L. Lock
2265 Anthony Hall, 474 S. Shaw Lane
East Lansing, MI 48824
E-mail: allock@msu.edu

INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Comparison of rumen and abomasal infusions of an exogenous emulsifier on fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. *By dos Santos Neto et al., page XXX.* We evaluated the effects of infusing an exogenous emulsifier (polysorbate-C18:1) into either the rumen or abomasum on fatty acid digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. Infusing 30 g/d polysorbate-C18:1 increased fatty acid digestibility. Compared with a ruminal infusion, abomasally infusing polysorbate-C18:1 tended to increase fatty acid digestibility. However, this may not be necessarily due to better emulsifying action because the abomasal infusion reduced fatty acid intake. In summary, abomasal and ruminal infusions both improved fatty acid absorption.

Supplemental Table S1. Plasma nonesterified fatty acids (NEFA), insulin, and glucose of cows infused with treatment

Item	Treatment ¹			SEM	Contrast ²	
	CON	RUM	ABO		CON vs. T80	RUM vs. ABO
NEFA, mEq/L	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.003	0.90	0.25
Insulin, µg/L	0.55	0.48	0.54	0.04	0.27	0.16
Glucose, mg/dL	64.0	63.4	64.7	0.85	0.96	0.30

¹Treatments consisted of no infusion (CON), infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1 (Tween-80, T80) into the rumen (RUM), and infusion of T80 into the abomasum (ABO).

²*P*-values associated with contrasts: (1) effect of T80 versus CON, and (2) the effect of ruminal infusion versus abomasal infusion.

Supplemental Table S2. Individual milk fatty acid (FA) yield of cows infused with treatments (n = 9)

Selected individual FA, ³ g/d FA	Treatment ¹			SEM	Contrast	
	CON	RUM	ABO		CON vs. T80	RUM vs. ABO
C4:0	34.1	35.3	35.3	2.33	0.38	0.99
C6:0	24.3	24.9	24.2	1.85	0.81	0.47
C8:0	14.6	15.1	14.6	1.12	0.77	0.49
C10:0	39.3	40.3	39.4	2.68	0.72	0.62
C12:0	46.9	48.1	47.0	2.81	0.74	0.60
C14:0	175	179	178	8.27	0.45	0.82
C14:1	12.3	12.1	12.3	1.03	0.86	0.71
C16:0	482	486	464	28.4	0.47	0.13
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	20.8	21.2	20.1	1.56	0.90	0.33
C18:0	122	128	124	11.8	0.61	0.64
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	2.32	2.26	2.44	0.11	0.81	0.26
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	2.01	2.22	2.50	0.09	0.01	0.04
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	3.56	3.82	3.68	0.26	0.45	0.60
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	4.92	4.87	4.81	0.36	0.74	0.82
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	240	246	258	14.0	0.06	0.06
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	5.85	6.06	6.45	0.28	0.15	0.20
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	22.6	23.3	23.9	1.04	0.03	0.24
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	2.71	2.50	2.85	0.15	0.74	0.01
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	3.85	4.01	3.96	0.22	0.46	0.77

¹Treatments consisted of no infusion (CON), infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1 (Tween-80, T80) into the rumen (RUM), and infusion of T80 into the abomasum (ABO).

²*P*-values associated with contrasts: (1) effect of T80 versus CON, and (2) effect of ruminal infusion versus abomasal infusion.

³Approximately 80 individual FA were quantified. Only select FA are reported in the table.

Supplemental Table S3. Individual milk fatty acid (FA) contents of cows infused with treatments (n = 9)

Selected individual FA, ³ g/100 g	Treatment ¹			SEM	Contrast ²	
	CON	RUM	ABO		CON vs. T80	RUM vs. ABO
C4:0	2.58	2.62	2.67	0.06	0.30	0.53
C6:0	1.84	1.84	1.82	0.06	0.93	0.69
C8:0	1.11	1.11	1.10	0.04	0.82	0.64
C10:0	3.00	2.98	2.95	0.10	0.66	0.68
C12:0	3.60	3.57	3.52	0.09	0.46	0.57
C14:0	13.4	13.4	13.4	0.19	0.92	0.82
C14:1	0.94	0.90	0.93	0.06	0.66	0.65
C16:0	36.6	36.9	35.1	0.81	0.08	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.57	1.58	1.56	0.11	0.95	0.81
C18:0	9.23	9.36	9.30	0.65	0.83	0.90
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.01	0.47	0.44
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.01	0.41	0.11
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.28	0.30	0.29	0.03	0.29	0.68
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.38	0.36	0.37	0.02	0.45	0.76
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	18.3	18.4	19.5	0.71	0.03	0.01
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	0.44	0.47	0.49	0.04	0.10	0.28
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	1.73	1.76	1.82	0.09	0.25	0.24
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	0.21	0.19	0.22	0.02	0.56	0.04
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.02	0.59	0.96

¹Treatments consisted of no infusion (CON), infusion of 30 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1 (Tween-80, T80) into the rumen (RUM), and infusion of T80 into the abomasum (ABO).

²*P*-values associated with contrasts: (1) effect of T80 versus CON, and (2) the effect of ruminal infusion versus abomasal infusion.

³Approximately 80 individual FA were quantified. Only select FA are reported in the table.

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